

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 2: Summary report on:
The development of pristine SI traceable reference materials for SMPs (0.1 μm - 10 μm) and NPs (< 0.1 μm), representative of partially degraded/naturally aged samples in complex food and environmental matrices, and for realistic polydisperse size distributions and irregular shapes

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:
Dansk Fundamental Metrologi A/S (DFM)

Due date of the deliverable: 31.05.2024

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 16.01.2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

21GRD07 PlasticTrace	1
1 Executive Summary	3
2 Introduction	4
3 Objectives	5
4 Strategy/Methodology	6
5 Results.....	7
5.1 Production of nanoPP test material	7
5.2 Characterisation of nanoPP test material	7
5.3 Homogeneity control of nanoPP	16
5.4 Stability control of nanoPP	21
5.5 Production of PP <10 µm	24
6 Outlook	26
6.1 Production of nanoPE	26
7 Conclusions	27
8 Annex.....	28

1 Executive Summary

This document reports the production and characterisation of SMPs ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) and NPs ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) as reference material candidates. It is focussed on different polymer types highly used in industry such as polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP). Since particles in this size are airborne, the particles were prepared in suspension. It is mandatory for reference materials to be homogeneous and stable what is really challenging for PE or PP suspension. Both polymers have a density smaller than water that let them swim at the surface. But without having a homogeneous suspension, the materials produced will never be a reference material. Furthermore, additional compounds as stabilizer will most probably affect the analytical results.

We developed a method to produce PE or PP NPs in water as stable suspension without using a stabilizer. The particles are broad size distributed as particles in the environment and oxidized at the surface. The particles are analysed for homogeneity with dynamic light scattering (DLS) and particle tracking analysis (PTA) according to their size distribution.

We also developed a procedure to make PP SMPs ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$). Method development is done and some characterisation started.

2 Introduction

This report describes the production and characterisation of SMPs and NPs reference material candidates produced in PlasticTrace. The particles should mimic particles in the environment according to size, shape and aging status. PlasticTrace is focussing on materials used in packaging that are either in direct food contact or can be found in the environment because of improper disposal or for example by spreading compost on the fields, where today a certain amount of plastic from shredded packaging may still be included as a by-product. The chosen polymers are PE and PP. These can degrade in the nature due to weathering conditions and will have an irregular shape with oxidized surface.

The nanoPE and nanoPP were produced by crushing PE or PP pellets in acetone with following sieving/filtration and change of the solvent to water.

PP (<10 μm) is also produced by crushing PP pellets but here in ethanol and under cooling in an ice bath. The particles are sieved and collected on a 1 μm filter, before dispersion in water with 1 mg/mL.

Homogeneity and stability control is absolutely mandatory in order to be able to name the developed test materials as reference materials in the future. For this purpose, homogeneity and stability tests according to the size distribution and number concentration of particles are carried out according to ISO 17034 and ISO Guide 35:2017

3 Objectives

NanoPP and nanoPE test material suspensions (in water) have been provided to the project partners together with pure MilliQ water as blank sample if needed.

The nanoPP is tested for homogeneity within the individual vials and in vial-to-vial variation according to particle size distribution and concentration.

Additional information on the nanoPP was collected by measuring the shape, the particle number per volume, confirmation of the particle type by mass-based methods and Raman.

The characterisation of nanoPE is in progress.

PP <10 μm could be produced in small quantities and is provided to selected partners for characterisation as water suspension.

4 Strategy/Methodology

PE and PP were chosen as reference material candidates, because they are highly used in packaging and will be in direct food contact.

The SMP and NPs are produced by milling with an UltraTurrax and subsequent sieving to achieve particles with environmental relevant properties such as irregular shapes, broad particle size distributions and different aging states mimicking particles in nature.

The NP particles were provided as particles in water suspensions without any stabiliser. Homogeneity control is done by DLS and PTA. Additional information is generated with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for shape and with TED-GC/MS and μ -Raman for polymer type as well as with AFM and MD-AF4.

SMP PP particles are provided in water with 0.025 wt% BSA as stabilizer. Homogeneity control was done by laser diffraction. Additional informations are provided by SEM for shape. Further informations are in progress.

5 Results

This chapter describes the production of SMP and NPs test material from plastic pellets and the characterisation of the material. The material is portioned, and the individual vials are tested on their homogeneity and stability.

Special care was taken to avoid contamination with plastics. Use of plastics in the lab is as much reduced as possible. The crushing equipment is made of stainless-steel.

5.1 Production of nanoPP test material ¹

NP test material is produced by crushing PP pellets with UltraTurrax and filtration afterwards (Figure 1). 25 g of PP pellets were put in a beaker. 250 ml Acetone is added. The beaker is cooled with ice for 30 min. The suspension is filtered via a pleated filter to get rid of the bigger particles. The solvent of the filtrate is then reduced to 10% by a rotary evaporator. 250 ml of MilliQwater is added. The water suspension is again handled with the rotary evaporator to get rid of the acetone (30 min at 100 mbar). The suspension is again filtered via the same pleated filter as before. The final produced nanoPP water suspension is bottled in 890 vials with 2 mL each.

Figure 1: Crushing PP pellets with UltraTurrax (left), filtration of crushed PP for fractionation (center) and bottled nanoPP (right) (source@BAM)

5.2 Characterisation of nanoPP test material

The particle size is one of the most important properties of MNP test materials. Other characterisation approaches are performed to ensure that the material is not altered e.g., by aging, during the production process and to have reference data to determine possible changes during storage. The material itself is mainly

¹ Hildebrandt, J. and A.F. Thünemann, Aqueous Dispersions of Polypropylene: Toward Reference Materials for Characterizing Nanoplastics. *Macromolecular Rapid Communications*, 2022: p. 2200874
<https://doi.org/10.1002/marc.202200874>

defined by the choice of starting material which is intentionally an artificially aged or unaged pure plastic granulate.

5.2.1 Dynamic light scattering

The **DLS technique** probes the particle motion optically in a suspension and the measurand is the average hydrodynamic particle size and the polydispersity. The suspended particles are illuminated with a coherent monochromatic light source. The light scattered from the moving suspended particles has a time-dependent phase imparted to it from the time-dependent position. The optical signal received from the particles are analysed and related to scattering efficiency and particle size. The modelling is based on Stoke-Einstein theory of Brownian motion of smooth spheres and is influenced by the viscosity and temperature.

Sample preparation

Samples were measured by DLS at native concentrations and without additives, by injecting 0.5-1 mL of the suspension in polystyrene cuvettes after homogenisation with pipettes, avoiding air bubbles that may skew the measurement results. The samples were then put into the instrument, and they were allowed to reach the measurement temperature for a minimum of 120 seconds before data acquisition begun.

Influence of non-spherical shape

DLS measures, by means of the diffusion coefficient, the average hydrodynamic size (radius/diameter) of the particles in the sample. This is the size of the sphere that diffuses with the same diffusion coefficient (average) of the sample. In the case of a monodisperse sample, the hydrodynamic size measured by DLS is ascribable to its mean size, averaged in all its dimensions.

What is reported

In accordance with ISO 22412:2017 "Particle size analysis — Dynamic light scattering (DLS)"², only the Z-average and PDI (polydispersity index) were considered for each measurement. The reported Z-averages and PDIs were calculated as the averages and standard deviations of the Z-averages and PDIs of the repeated measurements of each sample. Uncertainties of the results are also reported in section 5.

Uncertainty of the measurement result

Uncertainty of the measurements was evaluated as Type-A uncertainties.

5.2.2 Particle tracking analysis

Particle tracking analysis is a method where particles undergoing Brownian motion in a liquid suspension are illuminated by a laser and the change in position of *individual* particles over time is used to determine the particle size. PTA is a companion technique to DLS as it measures the hydrodynamic diameter. However, as PTA is based on the measurements of the position of *individual* particles it is not biased towards larger particle size which is typical the case for DLS. The minimal size detection limit depends on the optical properties of the sample material, typically above 10 nm for gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and above 40 nm to 50 nm for biological sample materials. The upper size detection limit is roughly 1000 nm.

Sample preparation

After gently shaking, the stock solution was diluted with ultrapure water gravimetrically 100 times to an optimum concentration range for the PTA instrument. The concentration range should ideally be between 1E7 particles / mL and 1E9 particles / mL. All aliquots were freshly prepared in duplicate and analysed immediately.

Experimental conditions

A NanoSight NS300 (PTA) system equipped with a laser module with a wavelength at 405 nm and a high sensitivity scientific complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (sCMOS) camera from Malvern Panalytical Ltd. (Malvern, UK) was used. Additionally, a syringe pump was connected to the Low-Volume-Flow-Cell

(LVFC). The measurements were conducted at room temperature, the instrument automatically determines the actual temperature for data analysis.

For instrument control and data analysis, the software version 3.4.003 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) was applied.

Prior to measurements the system performance was checked and the focus was determined by measuring 200 nm PS beads. Hereby, a qualification was considered adequate with size deviations below 6% (as advised by ISO 19430:2016 standard²). The camera level was evaluated using the automatic software settings. In general, PS 200 nm beads can be adequately characterised with a camera level of 9 (± 1).

The PS 200 nm beads suspension was freshly prepared by diluting the stock solution (1 wt.%) in UPW to around 0.200 mg/L (50,000x). The results were derived from 5 measurements with a capturing time of 60 s each. A syringe speed of 50 a.u. with a 1 mL syringe was considered adequate.

The following script (Table 1 below) was used for the NP measurements. Prior to the NP characterisation the camera level was determined by applying the automatic software function ("Auto setup" with "Auto setup camera level only"). Five consecutive measurements with a capture time of 60 s was conducted to track a significant number of particles and to obtain repeatable and accurate results.

Table 1: NanoSight measurement script (Software version NTA 3.4, MALVERN Panalytical) (Source@Postnova)

```
RECORDDILUTION 0
SETVISCOSITY WATER
CAMERASETTINGMSG
SYRINGELOAD 1000
DELAY 20
SYRINGELOAD 50
DELAY 10
REPEATSTART
CAPTURE 60
DELAY 1
REPEAT 4
SYRINGESTOP
PROCESSSINGLESETTING
EXPORTRESULTS
```

² ISO 19430:2016 - Particle size analysis - Particle tracking analysis (PTA) method

If the measured concentration is outside the ideal range, the concentration should be adjusted accordingly. The freshly prepared suspension should then be analysed again according to the description above.

Analysis

Data evaluation was performed using a “Detection Threshold” of 5. “Analysis info” was checked for warnings that might have been occurred during the analysis. Data reporting included average hydrodynamic sizes, particle concentration and D10, D50 and D90 values.

Influence of non-spherical shape

The particle sizes determined by PTA are hydrodynamic diameters. Thereby, the sizes are spherical equivalent diameters. PTA cannot distinguish between different shapes. Particles with a non-spherical shape will yield results equivalent to a diameter of a sphere that shows the same Brownian motion.

Uncertainty of the measurement result

Measurement results always show an uncertainty that can be due to temperature, solvent viscosity, self-diffusion coefficient and so on. The results are discussed according to the uncertainty components and their standard uncertainty

5.2.3 μ -Raman

Raman data was acquired with the aid of dielectrophoresis (DEP), an electrical phenomenon allowing concentration of particles in a very small volume through voltage, in order to achieve maximal local concentration at or near the focal point of the Raman microscope in negative DEP (nDEP). In Figure 2, spectra of the suspension without DEP aid (no voltage), the nanoparticles in suspension (nDEP), and a standard polypropylene sample unrelated to the nanoparticle fabrication (bulk), are shown. The nanoparticle samples show differences in the spectra with respect to common polypropylene: the most profound difference is the presence of two bands ascribable to C=O bond stretching at 1650 cm^{-1} and 1605 cm^{-1} , most likely due to the fabrication process of the particles.

Figure 2: Raman spectra of the nanoPP suspension without DEP aid (no voltage), the nanoparticles in suspension (nDEP), and a standard polypropylene sample unrelated to the nanoparticle fabrication (bulk) (Source@INRIM)

Table 2: Assignment of the wavenumbers detected in the Raman to the functional group

	Raman shift (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
a	2960	$\nu_a\text{CH}_3$
b	2924	$\nu_a\text{CH}_2$
c	2905	νCH
d	2869	$\nu_s\text{CH}_2$
e	2840	$\nu_s\text{CH}_3$
f	2723	νOH
g	1459	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3, \delta\text{CH}_2$
h	1463	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3$
i	1360	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3, \delta\text{CH}_2$
j	1330	$\delta\text{CH}, \tau\text{CH}_2$
k	1219	$\tau\text{CH}_2, \delta\text{CH}, \nu\text{CC}_b$
l	1168	$\nu\text{CC}_b, \rho\text{CH}_3, \delta\text{CH}$
m	1153	$\nu\text{CC}_b, \nu\text{C-CH}_3, \delta\text{CH}, \rho\text{CH}_3$
n	1036	$\nu\text{C-CH}_3, \nu\text{CC}_b, \delta\text{CH}$
o	999	$\rho\text{CH}_3, \delta\text{CH}, \omega\text{CH}_2$
p	973	$\rho\text{CH}_3, \nu\text{CC}_b$
q	940	$\rho\text{CH}_3, \nu\text{CC}_b$
r	900	$\rho\text{CH}_3, \rho\text{CH}_2, \delta\text{CH}$
s	842	$\rho\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{CC}_b, \nu\text{C-CH}_3, \rho\text{CH}_3$
t	810	$\rho\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{CC}_b, \nu\text{C-CH}_3$

5.2.4 Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were taken at a SEM of the type Supra 40 (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with a Schottky-field emitter, an SE (secondary electron) InLens detector, and a dedicated sample holder which enables transmission imaging (TSEM). The particles were prepared on a TEM grid by dropcasting of 2 to 6 μL suspension and dried in a desiccator. TEM grids were ozonated before use. The beam voltage was 10 kV and the working distance 4.8 mm. A SEM image of nanoPP particles is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SEM image of nanoPP

5.2.5 Atomic force microscopy

The nanoPP particle suspensions (in water) have been investigated thoroughly by other methods such as atomic force microscopy (AFM).

For the AFM measurements of the average diameter the nanoPP were prepared by drop casting a suspension (1% w/w) of 12 μl onto an atomically flat tilted mica surface (10 mm diameter) and letting it dry for 30 minutes, one month after production. The height of the particles is taken as an approximation of the diameter. The same sampling and measurement procedure was applied to a commercially available suspension of microspheres with nominal diameter of 500 nm (Figure 4). While the reference particles adhere to each other and form tongs of particles the nanoPP distribute over the surface more randomly perhaps with some tendency to aggregation. Some smaller particles or bumps are also seen on the substrate surface. The number of these small particles or bumps are not assessed thoroughly as part of this study. Including only particles with height $h > 60$ nm the average size of the nanoPP was found to be 116 nm in rough agreement with other measurements.

The AFM measurements have given valuable additional information but as part of the findings in this study it is concluded that they were not the best methods regarding time and robustness for getting the experimental evidence for the degree of homogeneity and stability.

Figure 4: top left is an AFM image and histogram of the size (height) distribution of the nanoPP (Sample 766). The profile in the middle is from the AFM image and show bumps equivalent to particles with diameter (height) up to app. 160 nm. The bottom AFM image and histogram are of commercial reference microspheres with a nominal size of 500 nm.

5.2.6 ThermalExtractionDesorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

TED-GC/MS measurements are carried out to ensure clear identification and mass quantification of the polymer using thermoanalytical methods. TED-GC/MS is a technique, which couples the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with a GC/MS system. The sample is heated from 25 to 600 °C under N₂ atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 K/min for extraction of decomposition gases. These gases are collected on a solid phaser adsorber and automatically transported to the GC/MS system. There, the gases are removed with slight increase in temperature, collected in a cold injection system before separation of the different molecules via the GC column. Analysis occurs in the mass spectrometer. Detailed information can be found in literature ^{3 4,5}.

³ Abdolapur Monikh, et al. (2023). Exposure protocol for ecotoxicity testing of microplastics and nanoplastics. Nat Protoc 18, 3534–3564 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-023-00886-9>

⁴ Duemichen, E. (2019): Automated thermal extraction-desorption gas chromatography mass spectrometry: A multifunctional tool for comprehensive characterization of polymers and their degradation products. In: Journal of Chromatography A, 1592, S. 133-142

⁵ Eisentraut, P. (2019): Two Birds with One Stone-Fast and Simultaneous Analysis of Microplastics: Microparticles Derived from Thermoplastics and Tire Wear. In: Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett, 5, 10, doi:10.1021/acs.estlett.8b00446

The total ion chromatogram as a result of the GC/MS run is suitable for the analysis of the decomposition products by screening for characteristic polymer marker molecules. The typical PP marker molecule can be detected after measurement of the dried PP particles of nanoPP suspension (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Typical PP marker detected by TED-GC/MS measurement of nanoPP with m/z 111, 69, 154 and 210 (Source@BAM)

5.2.7 Pyrolysis-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

Mass concentrations of nanoPP was also determined using pyrolysis GC-MS. The working principle of this technique is similar to that of TED-GC-MS, apart from the sample introduction. Most commonly, samples (solid) are pyrolyzed at 600 °C and directly transferred via a heated interface to the GC column where analytes (pyrolysis products) are focused on-column prior to for separation and detection. In our system, analysis was performed using a Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) coupled to an Agilent 7890A GC with an Agilent 5975C MS (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer was operated in single-shot mode with pyrolysis at 600 °C (1.0 min). The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were 320 °C, and the split ratio was 25:1. The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved using a Frontier Ultra ALLOY+-5 capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 µm film thickness, and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed at 40 °C (2 min) and ramped up by 20 °C/min until it reached 320 °C (25 min hold). The transfer line temperature was 320 °C, the ion source temperature was 230 °C, and the quadrupole temperature was 150 °C. The ion source was operated in SIM mode. For quantification of PP, the peak of 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-undecene (hetero form) at 9.85 minutes (m/z 69 and 111) was used, For calibration, a standard PP powder (PP Co-polymer CRT201.00 from CARAT GmbH, <100 µm) was dissolved in xylene (heat and sonication assisted), diluted and spiked in resulting masses of 0.25-5 µg in stainless steel pyrolysis cups. The nanoPP suspensions were homogenized by gentle shaking and 250 µL sub-sampled into pyrolysis cups for quantification. Solvents and water was removed by evaporation prior to analysis. Samples were run in randomized order, with triplicate calibration samples run throughout the series, also in randomized order. Six replicates of nanoPP suspensions were analysed and resulting concentration was 17±5 µg/mL (range 12-25 µg/mL, 28% RSD). Laboratory blank samples showed a background of 0.6 µg, this was not subtracted from the reported concentrations.

5.2.8 Multi-Detector-AF4 (MD-AF4)

Field-flow fractionation (FFF) is a separation technique without a stationary phase. The separation is achieved within a narrow, ribbon-like channel, wherein a laminar lateral flow is applied that results in a parabolic flow profile. Perpendicular to the channel flow a separation force is applied. The separation force can be realised by a second flow field (Asymmetrical Flow FFF short AF4) or a centrifugal force (CF3) or a thermal gradient (TF3). In AF4, the separation force interacts with the Brownian motion (Diffusion) of the sample constituents, as a result smaller particles, which have a higher diffusion coefficient, will be located closer to the centre and therefore will experience a higher lateral flow due to the parabolic flow profile. To allow the flow-field (cross flow) to leave the channel bottom (accumulation wall) the accumulation wall consists of an ultrafiltration membrane with a defined cut-off.

Additionally, the nanoPP aliquots were characterised by MD-AF4. AF4 measurements were performed using the AF4 system from Postnova (AF2000 MultiFlow FFF) including an autosampler, a fraction collector,

and a channel thermostat, which was equipped with an analytical fractionation channel with a tip-to-tip length of 277 mm, a shoulder width of 20 mm and a hip width of 5 mm. A regenerated cellulose (RC) membrane of 10 kDa molecular weight cut-off and a Mylar spacer of 350 μm height were placed in the fractionation channel. The AF4 system was connected to a UV detector, MALS (Multi-Angle Light Scattering) detector and DLS (Dynamic Light Scattering) detector.

For instrument control the AF2000 software version 2.2.0.1 and for data evaluation the NovaAnalysis version 2303 (Postnova Analytics) and the Zetasizer Software 8.02 (MALVERN Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) were applied. System performance must be checked after hardware changes of the system and at regular intervals for quality control purposes according to ISO/TS 21362:2018⁶ and manufacturer recommendations.

For the fractionation of nanoPP samples the fractionation channel was equipped with a 350 μm spacer and a 10 kDa RC membrane. A initial cross flow rate of 1.00 mL/min and an injection flow of 0.20 mL/min was used. The injection and focusing time was set to 5 min, the transition time to 0.2 min. After the focusing phase the cross flow rate was first kept constant for 0.2 min and then followed a power decay for 40 min to 0.10 mL/min. Afterwards a rinse step of 10 min minimised potential carry over effects and ensured reproducible conditions for subsequent measurements. A typical injection volume of 25 μL was used for the characterization measurements.

The sample was used as delivered, without any further preparation steps. The required amount of samples were transferred to an autosampler vial and measured at least 3 times using a fractionation and a direct injection method. Both, the fractionation and the direct injection method were performed using 0.2% NovaChem (Postnova Analytics) as an eluent. Additionally, blank measurements were performed by replacing the sample by eluent and applying the same method as for the sample measurements.

Hereby, MD-AF4 was used to determine the size using multi-angle-light scattering (MALS) and dynamic light scattering (DLS) and to identify differences in the size distribution between the aliquots. The high size-resolution ability of MD-AF4 was also applied to investigate homogeneity and storage stability to support the described results of PTA and Batch-DLS, respectively.

Figure 61: MD-AF4 Fractogram of a triplicate measurement of a nanoPP sample with MALS 90° scattering signal overlaying radius of gyration distribution and hydrodynamic radius distribution (Source@Postnova)

⁶ ISO/TS 21362:2018 – Nanotechnologies - Analysis of nano-objects using asymmetrical-flow and centrifugal field-flow fractionation

The successful fractionation using AF4 is displayed in Figure 6 above. A good recovery of greater 80% was determined, together with a high repeatability. The scattering intensity at 90° is overlaid with the radius of gyration distribution and the hydrodynamic radius distribution. The radius of gyration was obtained from the evaluation of 19 MALS angles using a sphere model to fit the angular dependent scattering data.

The ratio of radii of gyration to hydrodynamic radii was around 0.8, which indicates a nearly spherical shape, in particular in the range of 20 min to 30 min, where both techniques showed the highest intensity. Based on the UV concentration detector a mass fraction of 6.2% revealed a particle diameter smaller than 100 nm. In comparison the (Batch) PTA analysis allowed for the determination of the number-based fraction smaller than 100 nm to 27.5 % ($\pm 2.4\%$) (number-based distribution).

5.3 Homogeneity control of nanoPP

This section describes the analysis of the average size and number concentration within and between bottles/units.

5.3.1 PTA

The homogeneity of the nanoPP material was investigated by analysing 12 different aliquots. Every aliquot was prepared in duplicate and analysed 5 times according to the method described under 5.2.2. The PTA technique allows for the determination of hydrodynamic size and particle concentration, respectively, independent from each other. The homogeneity of the reference material was estimated for both endpoints.

At first the homogeneity regarding the particle size was assessed. Both particle size averages, mean and mode, were determined and evaluated. The following graphs illustrate the particle sizes from the individual aliquots. For the mean average particle size an overall large within-batch and within-sample repeatability was determined. The mode average particle size showed a lower within-batch and within-sample repeatability. No outliers were detected. All results of the homogeneity testing for each aliquot are displayed in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

To assess the homogeneity quantitatively a single factor ANOVA analysis was conducted. The mean particle size with its uncertainty ($k=1$) was $147.03 \text{ nm} \pm 3.15 \text{ nm}$ (relative uncertainty = 2.15 %) and the mode particle size was $120.94 \text{ nm} \pm 5.33 \text{ nm}$ (relative uncertainty = 4.43 %) respectively. In summary, the ANOVA results showed satisfying results for the mode average, but the p value was larger than the 5 % fit-for-purpose target. For the mean average results ANOVA analysis revealed no satisfying results as the F value was larger than the F_{critical} value.

Figure 7: Mean average hydrodynamic diameter from PTA measurements for 12 different nanoPP aliquots (Source@Postnova)

Table 3: Results of single factor ANOVA analysis for particle size and particle concentration measurements (n=12, results without the two outliers) (Source@Postnova)

	dh(mean) / nm		dh(mode) / nm		particle concentration / (particles/mL)
Uncertainty	3.15E+00		5.33E+00		1.37E+09
Relative standard uncertainty	2.15E-02		4.43E-02		7.91E-02
Relative standard uncertainty (%)	2.15		4.43		7.91

Figure 8: Mode average hydrodynamic diameter from PTA measurements for 12 different nanoPP aliquots (Source@Postnova)

Secondly, the particle number concentration was evaluated. An overall average of $1.74 \text{ E}+10$ particles / mL \pm $2.49 \text{ E}+9$ particles / mL (14.36 % with $k=1$) was determined. The particle number concentrations for all aliquots are illustrated in Figure 9.

Outlier test

A Grubb outlier test was conducted, and the results of ID 318 and ID 455 were identified as outliers using an alpha value of 0.05. The results of both influenced the outlier tests of each other, therefore the tests were performed without the other value. When excluding the two outliers from sample ID 318 and ID 455 an average of $1.75 \text{ E}+10$ particles / mL \pm $1.37\text{E}+9$ particles / mL (relative uncertainty of 7.91 %) was derived. A single factor ANOVA analysis revealed a satisfyingly low p value but a large F value.

Figure 9: Particle number concentration from PTA measurements for 12 different nanoPP aliquots, displayed with the overall average (orange line) (Source @ Postnova)

5.3.2 Multi-Detector-AF4 (MD-AF4)

Additionally to the PTA homogeneity testing MD-AF4 was used to support the results of PTA as an orthogonal method.

The nanoPP aliquots listed under 6.1 were characterised by MD-AF4. Samples were prepared in the same way as for PTA measurements, but no dilution was necessary. The freshly prepared samples were placed in the cooled autosampler. The fractionation by AF4 was highly repeatable, see diagram (Figure 10) below. The retention time corresponds to the hydrodynamic size with an overall variation 1.03% without any outliers. As a consequence, we can conclude that the hydrodynamic size is homogeneous, which is in line with the PTA homogeneity test results.

Figure 10: Retention time of MD-AF4 fractionations of 12 nanoPP aliquots (Source@Postnova)

Moreover, MALS analysis enabled the size determination independent from the fractionation. The determination of the radius of gyration distribution is displayed in the following figure, in particular the $R_{g,10}$, $R_{g,50}$ and $R_{g,90}$ results are listed. The scattering among 20 different angles (12° - 164°) was investigated and a spherical fit was applied to fit the angular dependent scattering intensities. The standard deviation reached a maximum value of 2.1% for the $R_{g,10}$. The $R_{g,10}$ results differed more compared to other results as the scattering intensity and size of the particles are low (Figure 11). In summary, the MD-AF4 homogeneity of the size, in this case hydrodynamic size and radius of gyration, respectively, of all 12 NanoPP aliquots was assessed. The MALS data can also be used to investigate the particle number concentration. The angular dependent scattering is dependent on size and particle number. To evaluate the particle number concentration and the homogeneous distribution of the particle concentration the area under the MALS 90° scattering signal was calculated and plotted, see the following Figure 10.

Figure11: Area of MALS scattering signal at 90° for 12 nanoPP aliquots after fractionation by AF4 (Source@Postnova)

The qualitative evaluation of the area corresponds very well with the PTA results, see Fig.11. Aliquots ID455, ID318 and ID617 are showing larger variations. A single factor ANOVA analysis revealed no outlier for the described MALS Area results. But the p value indicates significant difference between the aliquots. The results confirmed the particle concentration results of PTA measurements. The problematic aliquots were clearly identified with the same trends. As a consequence, the PTA sample preparation step was not causing the exceeding results of the mentioned aliquots.

Figure 12: Differential and cumulative size distribution of 12 nanoPP aliquots obtained by AF4-MALS (Source@Postnova)

5.4 Stability control of nanoPP

This section describes the stability of the average size, polydispersity index (PDI) and concentration over time. Stability was done with DLS measurements mainly. Additional tests were carried out with PTA to confirm the DLS results.

5.4.1 DLS

The results of the DLS stability control measurements are summarized in Figure 13. Individual results can be found in Annex (Table 6).

Figure 13: DLS results for 3 different vials for four different time points: Hydrodynamic diameter D_h (left) and Polydispersity Index (right) (Source @ INRiM)

5.4.2 PTA

The same trends were observed after PTA analysis (Figure 14). The hydrodynamic diameter (mode) differed 3.3% and the mean average only by 1.6%. The particle number concentration increased slightly with 2.3% (Figure 15). The average values were taken from 4 of 5 aliquots. As mentioned above aliquot ID027 showed significant different results also for PTA (already at t = 0), see the following two tables in Annex (Table 7 and Table 8).

Figure 14: PTA results of the particle size of the analysis of 4 different nanoPP aliquots at time t=0 month (left) and time t=10 month (right) (Source @ Postnova)

Figure 15: PTA results of the particle concentration of the analysis of 4 different nanoPP aliquots at time t=0 month (left) and time t=10 month (right) (Source @ Postnova)

5.4.3 MD-AF4 storage stability tests

The storage stability results using MD-AF4 indicated the same trends as Batch-DLS and PTA. The fractograms of the scattering signal at 90° for different NanoPP aliquots are displayed in the two figures below (Figure 13 and Figure14), where the first figure compares the aliquots at time point t = 0 months and the second figure overlays the results after 10 months. No significant fraction of agglomerates and no significant change in the particle size distribution was determined. The fractogram of aliquot ID027 shifted to larger retention times

compared to other aliquots but the same was detected for the start time suggesting stability over time. Overall, the repeatability decreased slightly after 10 months. The radii of gyration distributions were comparable, $R_{g,10}$ slightly higher after 10 months. But $R_{g,90}$ values were comparable, ID863 and ID696 even lower.

Figure 13: MD-AF4 Fractograms of NanoPP aliquots with the radii of gyration distribution for the time point t=0 months (Source @ Postnova).

Figure 14: MD-AF4 Fractograms of NanoPP aliquots with the radii of gyration distribution for the time point t=10 months (Source@Postnova)

5.5 Production of PP <10 μm

In addition to the MP >10 μm (REF Deliverable 1) and NP (<1 μm) reference materials, the PlasticTrace project also features activity on targeting reference materials for the 1-10 μm size range. This size range has proven challenging to i) produce and ii) isolate. However, it is currently an important size fraction of MP owing to the analytical challenges of quantifying and identifying such small MP particles in environmental and biological samples, which sit between techniques best suited to particles >10 μm (e.g. μFTIR and μRaman) and those optimised for particles <1 μm (e.g. DLS). Bottom-up synthesis methods are applicable to nano-sized particles, while top-down production by fragmentation of larger particles favours production of particles >0 μm , and while smaller particles are co-produced, their yields are typically very low⁷. The PlasticTrace partners have experience with a multitude of methods for production of < 10 μm plastic particles, and several methods have been tested without promising yields.

The final protocol selected in PlasticTrace consisted of fragmentation via wet grinding (UltraTurrax, 10 minutes on an ice bath) of PP pellets in ethanol (100%) followed by cascade sieving (500 μm , 90 μm , 45 μm) to first isolate the fraction <45 μm . A total of 150 g of PP in batches of 10 g in 100 mL ethanol was used as a starting material. Fragments collected on 500 μm sieves were subject to repeated grinding, and material collected on all sieves was re-suspended in ethanol and sieved two additional times. The resulting <45 μm isolate was concentrated by evaporation, filtered (10 μm) and finally collected on a 1 μm filter and rinsed with ethanol and dried. The weight of the 1-10 μm collected material obtained was ~20 mg, corresponding to a yield of 0.01%. Suspensions (1 mg/mL) were prepared in 0.025% BSA in water (MilliQ) via vortexing and sonication (bath and probe) to disperse the powder. This test material will be used by partners that have instrumentation for characterisation suitable for this particle size range. Stability and homogeneity controls will be analysed using laser diffraction. If sufficient material is produced, further material characterization will be attempted using PTA, FFF and SEM.

5.6 Characterisation of PP <10 μm

5.6.1 Scanning electron microscopy

SEM images were taken similar like described in section 5.2.4. Figure 15 shows the shape of PP < 10 μm particles provided with SEM image.

Figure 15: SEM image of PP <10 μm on a TEM grid

5.6.2 Homogeneity control with Laser diffraction

Laser diffraction was done with a device by Sympatec, Germany. The HELOS/BR was equipped with the wet dispersion system CUVETTE/6 means a cuvette with 6 mL volume was used. The complete suspension of one vial was diluted with another 5 mL MilliQ water and placed in the cuvette before measurement. The R1 lens was used. Evaluation occurred with MIE. 10 vials were measured with 5 repeat measurements for each individual vial. The summary is presented in Figure 16 as particle size distribution spectra indicating small particles mainly < 1 μm and a quite homogeneous distribution.

$x_{10,3} = 0,451 \pm 0,010 \mu\text{m}$ [2,196 %]	$x_{50,3} = 0,735 \pm 0,028 \mu\text{m}$ [3,787 %]	$x_{90,3} = 1,222 \pm 0,153 \mu\text{m}$ [12,488 %]
$x_{16,3} = 0,495 \pm 0,013 \mu\text{m}$ [2,598 %]	$x_{84,3} = 1,065 \pm 0,077 \mu\text{m}$ [7,263 %]	$x_{99,3} = 3,663 \pm 1,840 \mu\text{m}$ [50,224 %]
SMD = 0,691 μm	VMD = 0,853 μm	$C_{opt} = 5,884 \pm 0,606 \%$ [10,308 %]

⁷ Sørensen, L., Gerace, M.H., Booth, A.M. (2024). Small micro- and nanoplastic test and reference materials for research: Current status and future needs. Cambridge Prisms: Plastics 2, e13 [doi: 10.1017/plc.2024.13].

6 Outlook

6.1 Production of nanoPE

The production of nanoPE is in progress. First production generated in very small nanoplastic particles, but the concentration is very low. A new batch will be produced, where the particles in suspension must be enriched by rotary evaporation of the solvent or freeze drying.

7 Conclusions

Overall SMPs and NPs production is very challenging. Most difficulties are the limited yields combined with particle properties that lead to agglomeration of particles in suspension over time. If so, the test materials are not suitable as reference materials, where passing of homogeneity and stability is mandatory.

Irregular shaped nanoPP is proven to be produced and bottled in a way showing homogeneous distribution between individual vials. It passed homogeneity control and seemed to be stable over time (10 month).

NanoPE was also produced and bottled with irregular shape and broad size distribution. The first screening on particle size gave the impression that the size is near to 100 nm and hence nanoparticle definition, which makes the material very interesting. Unfortunately, the concentration is very low and partly too low for the analytics that could be applied. The experiment must be repeated with an additional step for enrichment of the particle numbers before bottling.

PP < 10 μm also passed the first homogeneity control but yields are really low.

In principle, first nanoplastic reference material candidates are produced and characterised that mimic particles in the environment addressing irregular shapes and broad size distributions.

8 Annex

Table 6: Batch-DLS results for 3 different aliquots for four different time points (Source @ INRiM).

	t = 0 months			t = 1 months			t = 3 months			t = 6 months		
	ID 044	ID 135	ID 732	ID 044	ID 135	ID 732	ID 044	ID 135	ID 732	ID 044	ID 135	ID 732
D_h (z-Average) / nm	174.7	175.4	174.5	177.9	177.9	178.6	178.1	177.4	175.6	184.0	179.7	176.7
SD / nm	4.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	2.1	2.9	3.7	4.2	1.8	7.4	2.8	0.5
PDI / -	0.062	0.070	0.05	0.052	0.058	0.064	0.079	0.066	0.052	0.047	0.086	0.055
SD / -	0.017	0.009	0.04	0.025	0.049	0.006	0.024	0.025	0.026	0.036	0.035	0.009
	t = 0 months			t = 1 months			t = 3 months			t = 6 months		
D_h (z-Average) ± standard uncertainty (expanded uncertainty) / nm	174.87 ± 0.39 (1.6)			178.13 ± 0.33 (1.4)			177.0 ± 1.1 (4.7)			180.1 ± 3.0 (13)		
PDI ± standard uncertainty (expanded uncertainty)	0.061 ± 0.008 (0.034)			0.058 ± 0.005 (0.022)			0.066 ± 0.011 (0.047)			0.063 ± 0.017 (0.073)		

taint y) / -				
--------------	--	--	--	--

Table 7:2 PTA results of the analysis of 5 different NanoPP aliquots at time t=0 (Source @ Postnova).

	ID 027		ID 206		ID 496		ID 696		ID 863	
	mean	sd error								
particle concentration / particles/mL	4.59E+09	2.29%	1.60E+10	2.60%	1.91E+10	2.52%	1.56E+10	3.83%	1.89E+10	3.85%
Dh (mean) / nm	166.3	2.4	146.4	1.6	146.7	2.5	148.9	1.3	146.6	0.6
Dh (mode) / nm	147.3	6	122.7	8.8	111.4	6.7	122.8	10.6	113	6.3
D10 / nm	118.9	2.6	99.7	1.6	96.9	1.4	101.6	1.2	99.9	1.4
D50 / nm	158.2	3.5	137.8	1.5	140	0.9	144.7	2.7	139.3	1.4
D90 / nm	219.8	6.8	207.3	5.3	201.9	8.6	198.8	4.5	203	3.6

Table 8: PTA results for 5 different aliquots after 10 months (Source @ Postnova).

	ID863		ID696		ID496		ID206		ID027	
	mean	sd error								
particle concentration / particles/mL	1.61E+10	3.31%	1.70E+10	1.95%	2.01E+10	1.41%	1.80E+10	2.57%	4.17E+09	12.8%
Dh (mean) / nm	145.1	2.9	139.2	0.9	145.3	1.3	150.0	1.6	157.0	3.0
Dh (mode) / nm	118.5	7.4	107.7	2.7	110.1	6.1	118.1	6.5	145.6	9.2
D10 / nm	98.6	1.8	96.3	1.7	101.0	1.9	99.0	1.0	107.5	5.2
D50 / nm	138.2	3.4	131.2	1.9	137.6	1.2	140.8	2.5	150.8	6.5
D90 / nm	199.4	2.4	190.6	5.2	200.6	4.7	206.8	4.9	215.4	8.7